

Information on Report of the Scientific Committee of the Food Safety Authority of Ireland on *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* and its links to Crohn's Disease

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Mycobacterium avium subsp. *paratuberculosis* (*Map*) is the causative agent of paratuberculosis or Johne's disease in cattle (JD). Similarities between JD in cattle and Crohn's Disease (CD), a type of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), in humans have prompted speculation on a possible role for *Map* in the pathogenesis of CD. In 2020, an *ad-hoc* subcommittee of the Scientific Committee of the FSAI reviewed primary, peer-reviewed papers published in the scientific literature between 2009 and 2019 which reference the putative link between *Map* and CD. Numerous studies published during that period provide evidence of an association between the presence of *Map* or human exposure to *Map* and the occurrence of CD. However, no new evidence has been published to substantiate the suggestion that this association is causal. The subcommittee also reviewed recently published papers (2009-2019) on the efficacy of thermal pasteurisation at inactivating *Map*. This review suggests that viable *Map* is unlikely to be found in milk that has been pasteurised at a time-temperature combination of at least 75°C for 20 seconds. Finally, the Committee considered current gaps in knowledge which impact on the ability to assess the risk that *Map* poses to human health and the risk that humans could be exposed to *Map* in food; further studies to address these knowledge gaps are suggested.